

FAILURE BEHAVIOR AND MORPHOLOGY OF HYBRID SHORT-FIBERS REINFORCED COMPOSITE UNDER THERMAL AND MECHANICAL LOADINGS

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SUMMARY: The mechanical property, microstructure morphology, and failure behavior of hybrid fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite containing defects were studied under coupled thermal and mechanical loading. The system investigated was hybrid short Al/C fibers reinforced polyaryletherketon composite, in which aluminum-fiber and carbon-fiber were 30 wt.-% and 10 wt.-%, respectively. First fracture testing of specimens with different artificial defects including notch and crack-like slot subjected to thermal and mechanical loading was carried out using three-point short-beam bending test; the effect of changing temperature on mechanical strength of the composite was then discussed; next failure mode and corresponding morphology of broken samples were systematically characterized by SEM; and finally, the macroscopic and microscopic failure behavior of the composite under coupled thermal and applied loads were addressed based on experimental data. Results show that high temperature is able to significantly affect macroscopic fracture mode, microscopic failure behavior, and ruptured morphology of the composite along with its mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid short-fiber, PAEK resin, high temperature, failure behavior, notch, slot, aluminum-fiber, carbon-fiber.

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composite consisting of two different fibers and single matrix is often advantageous over a regular composite. With alternative choice of fiber combination, it offers improved material properties such as thermal conductivity property, fracture toughness, and mechanical strength due to mixture effect of fibers. Therefore hybrid composite has been received considerably attention in the literature. A number of investigations have been made for performance analysis and characterization of hybrid continuous-fiber reinforced composite, for instance, selected papers like static problem [1], dynamic problem [2], fracture mechanics [3], and engineering application [4]. Meanwhile people are also increasingly interested in hybrid short-fiber reinforced composite as it can be used as a secondary structure to substitute steel materials due to its high strength to weight ratio and convenience of molding geometrical complex component. But most of works concentrated on the improvement of its physical properties including thermal and electrical conductivity [5-8], and surface treatment of fibers [9-10].

Like laminated composite for structural materials, however, hybrid short-fiber reinforced composite is sometimes serviced in more complicated environment such as high temperature and coupled thermal-mechanical load. Unfortunately, an available data about the influence

of changing temperature on mechanical property and failure behavior of a given material is very seldom. Furthermore the works done were only limited to consider the effect of single short-fiber on material property regarding high temperature [11-13]. It is thus necessary to perform laboratory tests to simulate actual operation environment of the hybrid composite and further to evaluate its structural integrity under practical service condition.

This study aims to investigate the effect of changing temperature on strength performance and failure behavior of hybrid short-fiber reinforced polymeric composite. The matrix material chosen is Polyaryletherketon (PAEK); it is a kind of new high performance semi-crystalline thermoplastic resin with glass transition temperature of around 170 °C, which combines excellent high-temperature property with retaining high elastic modules and high impact strength [14]. Reinforcements used are aluminum-fiber and carbon-fiber, respectively; the former is used for improving thermal conductivity property of the composite and the latter for enhancing mechanical performance. Since this kind of hybrid composite is a typical advanced composite material, it is able to be used as secondary component in some places where local service temperature is sometimes higher than 160 °C, such as aerospace motor-casing, heating-removal fan, and power pump. Hence the present study will provide important basis for the practical use of PAEK composite as lightweight component replacement. For this purpose, three-point short beam bending test were carried out for specimens containing different artificial defects under varying temperature; then microstructure and fracture mode of the specimens were viewed by optical microscopy, and failure behavior and morphology of the broken samples were observed in detail with scanning electron microscopy.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The matrix used is a commercial grade PAEK resin, called Ultrapek A1000, which is provided by BASF; aluminum-fiber and carbon-fiber are supplied by Japanese company. Carbon-fiber is a 3 mm long with a diameter of 7 μm , and aluminum-fiber, called as AlMg2.5 metallic-alloy fiber, is a length of 3 mm and its cross-section looks like a quasi triangular-shape with each side length of about 90 μm . Based on the previous work on its thermal and electrical property [5], the hybrid composite to be considered in this study will consist of 30 wt.-% of aluminum-fiber and 10 wt.-% of carbon-fiber. According to designation of ASTM D790, rectangular specimens for three-point short-beam bending test, in which the geometrical dimensions are 80 mm long, 10 mm wide and 4 mm thick, respectively, were manufactured directly by injection molding. The fundamental properties of the relevant materials are listed in Table 1.

Testing

Optical microscopy was utilized for the visualization of fiber alignment and orientation in the specimen and polarized light was used to view the crystallization of matrix in the composite. Fracture surface and morphology of broken samples were observed in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and samples were previously gold coated before SEM observation. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed for measuring glass transition temperature of the composite, and the results relevant to thermal properties of the composite with different contents of fiber measured by DSC are given in Table 2.

Table 1: Fundamental properties of constituents consisting of hybrid composite

Materials	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Density (g / cm^3)	Ultimate elongation (%)
Matrix A1000	104	4100	1.3	4
AlMg2.5 fiber	210	70000	2.68	7.5
Carbon fiber	3950	2380000	1.77	1.55
PAEK composite	106	10280	1.60	2.35

Table 2: Thermal properties for the hybrid composite with different fiber content

Sample No.	Matrix	Fiber content (wt. %)	T_g [$^{\circ}C$]	T_c [$^{\circ}C$]	T_m [$^{\circ}C$]
1	PAEK	0	169	339	393
2	PAEK	19.13	169	336	393
3	PAEK	40	170	327	380

Note: T_g denotes glass transition temperature, T_c initial melting temperature, and T_m melting temperature; sample 2 only contains aluminum-fiber and sample 3 contains 30 wt.-% aluminum-fiber and 10 wt.-% carbon-fiber.

Three different kinds of specimens containing different artificial defects were prepared for bending test. The artificial defects with semi-notch and crack-like slot were machined into the center on the edge of each specimen. The geometrical size and configuration of defects are described in the following: the slot is approximately 0.4mm wide and the depth from the edge is 2 mm long; the notch has a radius of $R=2$ mm and depth from the edge is also 2mm long.

With temperature ranging from room temperature to 200 $^{\circ}C$, short beam three-point bending test were conducted in Instron 4515 universal test machine with a temperature chamber, and loading rate was chosen to be 5 mm/min. After testing, some samples were cut from section of the fractured specimens for observing their fracture behavior and morphology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microstructure details

In general, injection-molded hybrid short-fiber reinforced composite is fairly inhomogeneous because most of the fibers are aligned in the direction of mold-filling. Fig.1, which illustrates the fiber distribution and orientation along the transverse and longitudinal direction, shows the fibers are preferentially oriented parallel to mold-filling direction. Aluminum-fibers are tendency to the longitudinal direction, in which fiber length points to the flow direction of mold-filling. However, in the direction of transverse section, there is very seldom for fiber length to locate along this direction. As a result, the microstructure of the composite made

through injection molding displays anisotropic property, which will also influence fracture behavior of the material.

a) along transverse direction (200x) b) along longitudinal direction (200x)
Figure 1: Profile of fiber distribution and orientation

Effect of changing temperature on composite strength

The relationship between bending stress and strain of the specimen without artificial defect subjected to different temperature is depicted in Fig. 2. From this figure, we can see that at room temperature, once the applied stress reaches yielding stress of the material, the composite breaks immediately, with no visible plastic deformation. When temperature is raised to 100 °C, the relationship of material 's stress-strain still keeps linear basically without the effect of temperature and the load-bearing capability of the composite reduces a little. The value of maximum stress at this case is only smaller than that of its counterpart at room temperature by a quarter and the magnitude of Young's modulus is almost same each other.

Figure 2: The effect of changing temperature on material strength (without defect)

For the case of 200 °C, however, the composite softens greatly and displays nonlinear plastic deformation feature for the high temperature; the whole stress-strain curve looks smooth, and the amount of plastic deformation is considerably large. Consequently, the load-bearing capability of the composite considerably reduces once temperature is above a certain value. Higher temperature makes inherent energy of the material be raised so movement of

molecular becomes more easier. When temperature is risen up to 200 °C, namely higher than glass transition temperature of the resin, the reduction in strength of the composite is extremely large, irrespective of how much of the content of reinforcement fiber; the maximum stress at this time is only half a value at room temperature. Furthermore, the Young's modulus also decreases dramatically, which is only 20% of Young's modulus at room temperature. Comparing to strength performance of the material, the influence of temperature on the composite's stiffness is significantly larger than that of its influence on composite's strength. Similar feature can also be seen from specimens with artificial defect, which will further be discussed in an another separated paper [15]. Therefore, high temperature not only influences strength of the composite but also changes the deformation behavior of the composite. Moreover, when temperature is well above glass transition temperature of resin, the effect of fiber orientation becomes less significant due to easy movement of resin molecular. So high temperature will cause resin damage and shorten residual life of the composite.

Effect of defect type on material property

Figure 3 shows the effect of different defect shape on the strength of the composite at room temperature and the associated mechanical properties measured are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: The effect of defect type on composite strength at room temperature

Defect type	Young's modulus (MPa)	Maximum load (KN)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Displacement at break (mm)	Strain at break (%)
non-defect	5343	1.164	173.20	1.209	4.48
notch	4617	0.500	75.58	0.495	1.83
slot	4485	0.488	71.94	0.481	1.79

Figure 3: The effect of defect shape on the strength of the composite (T=24°C)

Because of stress concentration, like metal material, load-bearing capability of the composite containing defect substantially reduces. In this figure, it can be seen that the maximum stress specimen containing artificial defect can undertake is much smaller than that of specimen

without defect. Usually, their stress values are less than a half stress value of specimen without defect (see Table 3). In addition, the deformation curves of specimens with and without defect are also quite different. Regarding specimen without defect, its stress increases with the increase of strain until final fracture of specimen; whereas for the specimens with defect, their stress first increases with increasing of strain and then the stress in the specimen rapidly decreases due to resin yielding. This implies once resin material enters yielding, specimen will immediately fail without any softening-strengthening phenomena. This is also the same trend for both specimens with defect and specimen without defect. However, for the specimens with notch and slot, their stress-strain curve and tendency look very similarly. The reason is as follow: due to stress concentration, stress at the tip of the notch and slot will reach yielding stress of resin and surrounding materials are thus blunted; but stresses a little far away from the tip zone are still less than yielding stress of the resin, and the materials nearby the tip zone are surrounded by a large amount of linear-elastic material. In this instance, stress at the tip of notch and slot will be relaxed and redistributes by means of plastic deformation of the resin to let tip displacement open largely than before. Moreover, under the condition of high temperature, the material possesses larger ductility and permits bigger displacement value at the tip of defect in comparison with that at room temperature. As a result of these, local stress concentration is not critical to some extent to the magnitude of width at the tip of defect for the tough resin like PAEK. Instead the elastic-plastic behavior of resin material becomes important. Therefore if the resin is a tough material, the critical magnitude of the width at defect tip is a little dependent on the extend of stress concentration caused by defect type but be more dependent on their material's elastic-plastic behavior. This maybe the main reason why the stress-strain curves of the specimens with notch and slot resemble one another.

Macroscopic fracture mode

For three kinds of specimens, the macro fracture mode of the composite is dependent largely upon temperature. Visual observation of the broken samples indicates that the hybrid composite dissipates fracture energy primarily by a combination of saw-tooth deflection of fracture surface, plastic deformation of specimen, as well as fiber's pull-out, debonding, and rupture (see Fig. 4, and the detailed analysis will be addressed in the following section on microscopic failure behavior).

Figure 4: The macroscopic fractography of specimens containing notch at room temperature

Fig. 5 shows fracture profile of three kinds of specimens with varying temperature. At room temperature, the fractured specimen keeps fundamentally original shape and the fractured section of three specimens almost separates in the way of brittle. It means that for brittle fracture mode there is very little energy dissipation consumed by plastic deformation prior to

final failure. With the increase of temperature, failure manner is changed from quasi-brittle mode at room temperature to ductile mode at 100 °C. At the time when temperature is equal to 100 °C, the composite possesses more ductile behavior due to increase of inner energy and the whole specimen occurred a little plastic bending.

a) $T=24^{\circ}\text{C}$

b) $T=100^{\circ}\text{C}$

c) $T=200^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 5: Optical micrography of the fracture profiles for different temperature

Compared to its original shape, the geometrical shape of the fractured specimen happen variation; most obviously, fracture surfaces for specimens with notch and slot still connect each other after failure. That implies ductile fracture will consume a certain amount of fracture energy before breaking through plastic deformation as specimens have undergone a larger bend plastic deformation. As temperature is risen to 200 °C, failed specimen displays large plastic deflection. In this circumstance, fracture surface of all three specimens do not break apart; furthermore, deformation process exhibits non-linear plastic flow due to viscous-plastic stretching of matrix. This means the movement and slide of polymer molecular become more easier for high temperature, and resin material tends to be viscous-plasticity behavior. Thus the characteristic of resin damage at high temperature will be viscous-plastic stretching instead of only yielding. For this reason, fracture surfaces of specimens at 200 °C keep together. All of these cases demonstrate the macro fracture feature of the composite has a great good relation with temperature.

Microscopic failure behavior

SEM photography of the fracture surface for hybrid composite with changing temperature are shown in Figs 6-8.

In a sense of micro-level, the fundamental failure behavior of the hybrid composite comprises fiber pull-out (Fig. 6(a)), fiber debonding (Fig. 7), fiber rupture (Fig. 8), and plastic deformation of matrix (Fig. 6 (b) and (c)). The most obvious characteristic for the failure of the composite is that morphology of the matrix is extremely quite different with changing temperature (Fig. 6). At room temperature, matrix morphology is basically flat with cusp and exists a little shear band with brittle behavior; matrix morphology at 100 °C gets rough and appears many ductile dimples, illustrating deformation is in the manner of elastic-plasticity; while $T=200$ °C, fractography of matrix looks like a shape of mop filling with fibrils, exhibiting viscous-plastic flow deformation is caused by excessive high temperature.

a) $T=24^{\circ}\text{C}$

b) $T = 100^{\circ}\text{C}$

c) $T=200^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig. 6: The effect of changing temperature on morphology of matrix

Moreover, the interface of matrix and fiber becomes severe due to difference of their thermal expansion coefficients. However, there is no obvious feature to well characterize the effect of defect type on the morphology owing to insensitivity of tough matrix to defect type. The interface between carbon-fiber and matrix is dependent to great extent on their position and place. Two cases for bonding surface of carbon fibers at room temperature are depicted in Fig. 6 (a) and Fig. 7(a). Fig. 6(a) demonstrates excellent interface of carbon-fibers and Fig. 7(a) poor situation for the interface of carbon-fibers. Why is the interfacial surface of carbon-fiber fully different for the same process condition? The crystallization and extend of resin

PAEK on the surface of carbon-fiber account for this result. With reference to Fig. 6(a), there exist a very thin layer of resin film adhere to the surface of the carbon-fiber. This thin layer is resulted directly from crystallization of PAEK resin shown in Fig. 9, in which the interface between resin and carbon-fiber bonds strongly. By contrast, there is very clean on the surface of carbon-fiber shown in Fig. 7, which indicates there is no any crystallization thin layer adhesive to the surface of carbon-fiber. This event is, in fact, closely related to cooling way of the extruded reinforced pellets and molding process of the specimen when molded by injection machinery. At a time when hybrid-fiber reinforced PAEK pellets are extruded, they need to be cooled fast to fix their shape. If the resins are located inside the pellet, they are gradually cooled and thus have relatively more time to crystallize on the surface of the fibers; but if the resins situate on or near the surface of the pellet, they are immediately cooled and thus create brittle amorphous structure without any crystallization.

a) $T = 24^{\circ}\text{C}$

b) $T = 200^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 7: Carbon-fiber pull-out and debonding

Fig. 8: The morphology of ruptured aluminum-fiber

Fig. 9: The crystallization photo of matrix on the surface of aluminum- and carbon-fiber

Similarly, when specimen is manufactured from the pellets by injection machine, cooling of molding tool also affects the crystallization of resin. Resins lying on the surface of specimen are usually not easy to crystallize for the fast cooling of tool, and resins near the center of the specimen are easy to be crystallized due to longer period of cooling so that they form crystallization morphology. It is these reasons that result in completely different interface

between carbon-fiber and matrix. Another interesting thing about interface of the carbon-fiber is worthwhile to noting there is no fracture phenomena of the fiber due to its too short.

Comparing with carbon-fiber, however, the interfacial bonding between aluminum-fiber and matrix is always relatively poor. As indicated in Table 1, elongation rate of aluminum-fiber is much larger than that of carbon-fiber, but larger than that of resin. When applied stress is above yielding stress of resin, the tensile stress will automatically transfer to aluminum-fiber, making it be elongated longitudinally and contracted transversely. With the increase of tensile stress, the cross-section of the aluminum-fiber is shrunken greatly until its final rupture (see Fig. 8), resulting in the surface of aluminum-fiber to be separated from matrix. While this pattern is equivalent to pull-out of carbon-fiber, their ruptured section is not a smooth flat, but looks like steep rock. Besides, for the reason of high temperature, the number of pull-out of carbon-fiber at 200 °C is more than that at room temperature (see Fig. 7); furthermore, carbon-fibers seem to be moved obviously due to large viscous-plasticity stretching of matrix. These further illustrate temperature is a crucial factor to influencing both deformation morphology of matrix and fiber interface.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental results of PAEK composite with varying temperature and failure analysis for broken samples, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- (1) Micro failure behavior of the composite is closely related to temperature. Matrix morphology at a room temperature is cusp flat with a small brittle shear bands, at 100 °C matrix surface gets rough and exists a lot of ductile dimples, and in the case of 200 °C matrix deformation looks like a mop consisting of fibrils with a characteristic of viscous-plastic flow.
- (2) The macro failure behavior of the composite is also affected by high temperature. With the increase of temperature, failure behavior is changed from quasi-brittle mode at room temperature to ductile mode at 100 °C; when temperature equals 200 °C, fracture mode becomes large plastic deflection.
- (3) The interface situation between fiber and matrix is dependent mainly upon crystalline degree of resin and service temperature. With high crystallization, the interface bonds strongly, and vice versa. Furthermore, the interface of resin and fibers becomes poor with the temperature; high temperature tends to weaken the fiber/matrix interfacial bond because of the difference in their thermal expansion coefficients.
- (4) The temperature effect on strength performance of the composite is very significant. With the increase of temperature, the strength reduction of the composite is extremely large and the strength at 200 °C is only half a value at room temperature. However, as PAEK resin is a kind of tough material, the type of defect only influences magnitude of local stress concentration, but not influences failure behavior of the material.

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